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Empowering High School Science Learning Through Technology Integration

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Abstract

This quantitative action research study explored how professional development centered on interactive technology affected teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies in grades 9–12 science classes at Salt Cedar High School. The study addressed the concern that many teachers lacked confidence in implementing technology-based, student-centered instructional practices, which contributed to lower levels of student engagement. The guiding research question examined how participation in professional development influenced teachers' confidence in applying engagement strategies. Four high school science teachers participated in the study and completed pre- and post-surveys using a 5-point Likert scale to measure changes in confidence and technology use. Following WGU's exempt research guidelines, the study relied solely on teacher-reported quantitative data. The results showed consistent growth in mean survey scores across all eight items, reflecting increased confidence in integrating digital tools, facilitating inquiry-based learning, troubleshooting technical issues, and using technology for real-time formative assessment. Overall, the findings indicated that focused, hands-on professional development strengthened teacher confidence and encouraged more purposeful use of interactive technology to support student engagement in high school science classrooms.

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Topic and Problem	5
Topic.....	5
Problem Statement.....	6
Root Causes of the Problem	6
Research Question(s).....	8
Topic and Problem Conclusion.....	8
Chapter 2: Review of the Literature	10
Literature Review Introduction.....	10
Student Engagement and Academic Success.....	11
Positive Impact of Using Interactive Technology.....	11
Importance of Professional Development.....	12
Equitable Technology.....	13
Conclusion.....	13
Chapter 3: Research Methodology.....	14
Research Design.....	14
Research Question(s).....	14
Participants.....	14
Data Collection Instruments and Methods.....	15
Data Analysis.....	18
Data Security and Confidentiality.....	19
Conclusion.....	19
Chapter 4: Results.....	20
Results Introduction.....	21
Findings.....	21
Answers to the Research Questions.....	23
Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusion	26
Discussion and Conclusion Introduction	26
Problem Solutions	26

	4
Limitations	27
Implications.....	30
Further Investigation	32
References	34
Appendix A	37
Appendix B	38
Appendix C	39

Chapter 1: Topic and Problem

Topic

My action research centered on enhancing student engagement in high school science classes for grades 9 through 12 by incorporating interactive technology. This study was specifically focused on Salt Cedar High School (pseudonym), where I taught various science courses. The issue of low engagement was noted not only in my classroom but also by other science teachers within the department. Our student body remained diverse, with many students continuing to face challenges in accessing learning resources outside of school, making effective engagement strategies essential during class time. This topic was important to the education field because it addressed key factors, such as student motivation and active participation, which were crucial for academic success and developing the skills necessary for the modern world. From a leadership standpoint, improving student engagement was a priority that extended beyond individual classrooms and tied into the school's broader goals of enhancing teaching quality and reducing achievement gaps. School and department leaders highlighted the need for more technology-based, student-focused instructional approaches in science, making this research highly relevant to current school initiatives. The project was supported by evidence, including observations of decreased participation in traditional lessons, feedback from students seeking more interactive learning, and discussions within the department about engagement challenges. By focusing on schoolwide concerns and utilizing resources already available at the site, this research offered a practical and potentially scalable solution. Branching Minds (2021) stated that

student engagement acted as the key factor that bound and drove all areas of student learning and personal growth.

Problem Statement

At Salt Cedar High School, future efforts to improve science instruction faced challenges stemming from teachers' limited confidence in using innovative student engagement strategies. Many educators continued to seek ways to effectively integrate interactive, technology-enhanced, and inquiry-based methods that fully immerse students in the learning process. Without this confidence, instruction likely remained traditional and teacher-centered, leading to low participation, reduced curiosity, and weak connections to scientific concepts. As a result, students' motivation and achievement in science declined, limiting their long-term interest in STEM fields. This challenge was amplified by a diverse student population, some of whom faced ongoing barriers such as limited access to educational technology outside of school. Building teachers' future readiness and confidence in applying dynamic engagement strategies was essential to transform science classrooms into inclusive, hands-on, and inspiring environments that prepared students for success in an increasingly STEM-driven world.

Root Cause(s) of the Problem

From a leadership perspective, the ongoing challenge of low student engagement in grades 9–12 science classes at Salt Cedar High School could be traced primarily to teachers' lack of confidence in implementing innovative engagement strategies. This lack of confidence influenced several interconnected areas that affected both teaching practices and student learning outcomes.

One major factor was the inconsistent integration of interactive technology across the science department. Although the school provided digital tools such as Chromebooks and online

platforms, many teachers felt unsure about how to use these resources effectively to enhance inquiry, collaboration, and hands-on learning. Limited professional development opportunities have hindered teachers from acquiring the skills and confidence necessary to design engaging, technology-rich lessons. As Hew and Cheung (2014) noted, the successful use of blended learning combining face-to-face and digital instruction could significantly increase student satisfaction and participation.

Another contributing factor was the persistence of traditional, teacher-directed instructional approaches. Educators who lacked confidence in managing student-centered activities often defaulted to lectures and structured lessons to maintain control and pacing. While this approach covered content efficiently, it minimized opportunities for students to explore concepts independently or engage in deeper discussions. Department-level discussions revealed that some teachers felt uncertain about balancing curriculum requirements with more interactive and exploratory learning strategies.

Additionally, inequitable access to technology outside of school compounded this issue. Teachers hesitated to assign digital, inquiry-based tasks out of concern that not all students had the necessary tools or internet access at home. This further limited their confidence in fully implementing technology-enhanced learning experiences.

Finally, the absence of consistent collaboration among teachers contributed to the problem. Without structured opportunities to share engagement strategies, observe one another's practices, and reflect on what worked, teachers' confidence in adopting new approaches remained low.

Leadership teams recognized that building a culture of collaboration and shared professional learning was essential to empowering teachers and sustaining effective engagement practices.

Addressing these root causes required a coordinated leadership effort focused on strengthening teachers' confidence through ongoing professional development, equitable access to resources, and collaborative support systems. By investing in teacher capacity and fostering a growth-oriented culture, Salt Cedar High School could create a more dynamic, inclusive, and engaging science learning environment.

Research Question(s)

1. How does participating in professional development impact the teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies?

Topic and Problem Conclusion

This action research project, which focused on boosting student engagement in grades 9–12 science classes by using interactive technology, was important because it addressed a real and ongoing need at Salt Cedar High School. Observations, teacher conversations, and department discussions all showed the same concern: students were not fully engaged, and this affected how much they participated and how deeply they understood the science content. Even though the school had access to tools like Chromebooks and online platforms, many teachers did not feel confident using these resources in ways that encouraged hands-on learning, collaboration, or inquiry-based activities. As a result, instruction often stayed traditional and teacher-led, which did not fully support the diverse learners in our classrooms.

These challenges made it clear why this project was necessary. Without taking steps to improve engagement, students would have continued to lose interest in science, struggle academically, and miss out on opportunities that could have led them into STEM fields. Many of

our students also faced barriers to accessing resources outside of school, which meant that engaging, meaningful learning needed to happen during class time. From a leadership standpoint, addressing this problem aligned with our school's larger goals of improving instruction, ensuring equity, and helping students succeed.

Overall, this project was needed to help teachers feel more confident using technology, make better use of the tools the school already had, and create more engaging, student-centered science classrooms. By exploring and applying strategies that used technology to support learning, the study responded to a real schoolwide concern and set the stage for stronger engagement and deeper learning in science.

Chapter 2: Review of the Literature

Literature Review Introduction

This research explores how implementing interactive technology alongside focused professional development can improve student engagement in high school science classrooms at Salt Cedar High School. The core issue being investigated is the consistently low level of student engagement in grades 9–12, which is evident through a lack of participation, frequent distractions, and minimal involvement with science content. This disengagement affects academic performance and may discourage students from pursuing future opportunities in STEM fields. Additionally, many students have limited access to technology outside of school, making it vital to maximize in-class engagement strategies.

To address this problem, the literature review is organized around four central themes. The first theme emphasizes the strong link between student engagement and academic success, showing that students who are engaged cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally tend to achieve better outcomes. The second theme examines the positive impact of using interactive technology such as digital games, simulations, and blended learning to enhance student interest and involvement. The third theme focuses on the importance of professional development in helping teachers effectively use technology in their lessons. The final theme highlights the role of equitable technology access in supporting all students, especially those facing resource limitations at home.

These themes directly support the research questions, which explore the impact of professional development on teacher confidence in using engagement strategies and the

effect of interactive technology on student participation. Literature provides a foundation for the study's goal: to design and implement a schoolwide approach that improves science engagement through technology integration and effective teacher training.

Student Engagement and Academic Success

Student engagement is a fundamental factor influencing academic achievement, motivation, and long-term commitment to learning. Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2004) developed a core framework that defines engagement across behavioral, emotional, and cognitive dimensions, demonstrating a strong link between engagement levels and academic outcomes. Building on this, Wang and Eccles (2013) found that students' engagement improves when they perceive their teachers as supportive and their coursework as meaningful. The work of Branching Minds (2021) supports these findings, noting that engaged students tend to display increased motivation and more constructive classroom behavior. Collectively, these studies stress the need for actively engaging students, particularly in science courses, where content can often feel abstract or disconnected from students' lived experiences.

Positive Impact of Using Interactive Technology

A growing body of evidence confirms that digital tools can play a transformative role in boosting student engagement in science education. Lahlali et al. (2023) demonstrated that interactive simulations, such as PhET, significantly elevate students' motivation, collaboration, and academic performance. Nadeem, Oroszlanyova, and Farag (2023) similarly observed that game-based learning environments effectively increased engagement in online contexts, though they cautioned that the structure of game

mechanics matters. Hew and Cheung (2014) found that combining face-to-face instruction with digital components known as blended learning led to greater student satisfaction and involvement. Additional studies by Asare et al. (2023) and Ambusaidi, Al Musawi, and Al-Balushi (2018) found that virtual labs improved learners' interest and attitudes toward science when compared with traditional instructional methods. These findings are especially useful for secondary schools like Salt Cedar, where interactive technologies have the potential to reinvigorate science learning experiences.

Importance of Professional Development

Introducing technology into the classroom is most effective when supported by meaningful professional development. Darling-Hammond, Hylar, and Gardner (2017) emphasized that effective PD includes sustained, collaborative learning opportunities that involve coaching and hands-on practice. Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2010) pointed out that educators' personal beliefs and school environments strongly influence their willingness to embrace new technologies. The SAMR model developed by Puentedura (2014) offers a clear roadmap for teachers to move from basic digital use to transformative classroom practices. Similarly, Falloon (2020) proposed the Teacher Digital Competency (TDC) framework, which underscores the importance of combining technical skills with instructional design expertise. Liu et al. (2024) added that teachers who actively participate in digital professional learning communities are more likely to apply technology successfully. Collectively, these sources emphasize that thoughtful and continuous PD is key to equipping teachers with the tools and confidence needed to foster student engagement through technology.

Equitable Technology

According to Bergdahl et al. (2024), student engagement is essential for academic success, particularly in blended and technology-enhanced learning environments. To truly enhance engagement through technology, students must have consistent and equitable access to digital tools. Bebell and O'Dwyer (2010) reported that programs providing each student with a device (1:1 computing) helped improve digital skills, collaboration, and classroom participation, though the focus was more on access than instruction. Branching Minds (2021) and Lahlali et al. (2023) both emphasized that students without adequate access outside of school often face motivational challenges and learning gaps. These studies collectively highlight the importance of ensuring all students, especially in schools like Salt Cedar with limited resources, have the tools they need to engage meaningfully in technology-enhanced learning.

Conclusion

The literature demonstrated that student engagement was essential for academic growth, particularly in science education. Engaged students, whether through behavior, emotion, or thinking, were more likely to succeed academically, stay motivated, and participate positively in class. Research also supported the value of interactive technology, such as simulations, digital games, and virtual labs, in making science more engaging and accessible. However, the success of these tools depended heavily on teachers receiving effective, ongoing professional development. Additionally, without equitable access to technology, many students, especially in underserved schools, missed out on these benefits.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

Research Design

This action research employed a quantitative design to investigate how professional development focused on interactive technology affected teachers' confidence in high school science classes. In compliance with WGU's exempt research guidelines, data were collected solely from teacher participants. Quantitative data were gathered through pre- and post-surveys administered to the participating teachers to assess changes in their confidence levels and their use of technology.

This design aligned closely with the approved research questions by providing measurable outcomes while remaining in full compliance with WGU's exempt research guidelines. The quantitative approach enabled the assessment of changes in teachers' confidence through teacher-reported survey data. Pre- and post-surveys completed by teachers provided insight into shifts in their perceived confidence and instructional use of interactive technology. This approach supported the core purpose of action research to inform and improve teaching practice through data-informed decision-making, without collecting data directly from students.

Research Question(s)

How does participating in professional development impact the teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies?

Participants

This action research project involved a small group of 2 to 4 science teachers working at a rural high school in the southwestern region of the United States. These

teachers instructed students in grades 9 through 12 across various science courses such as biology, chemistry, and physical science. The participating educators came from diverse cultural backgrounds, including Asian, Native American, and White, reflecting part of the school's broader demographic composition. They ranged in age from their late 30s to early 50s and all held at least a bachelor's degree, with some having earned advanced degrees. Their teaching experience spanned from a few years to more than 15 years, offering a balanced perspective between novice and veteran educators regarding technology integration and student engagement.

In addition to teacher participants, the research also involved the students they taught as indirect participants through observation and data collection related to engagement levels. The student population consisted primarily of individuals from economically disadvantaged households, many of whom qualified for free or reduced lunch. The school also served students receiving special education services and included representation from tribal communities, foster care, and military families. Students' engagement data, such as participation levels, interaction with digital tools, and academic task completion, were collected anonymously and analyzed to assess the effectiveness of technology-enhanced instructional strategies.

These selected teachers participated in professional development focused on integrating interactive technology into their science instruction. Their implementation of these strategies provided the basis for examining shifts in student engagement. All data collected remained confidential, and the study was conducted in full compliance with

WGU IRB policies to protect the rights and privacy of all participants, including both teachers and students.

Data Collection Instruments and Methods

This action research project focused on collecting quantitative data to measure how professional development (PD) influenced teachers' confidence in using interactive technology to increase student engagement in high school science classes. The main tool for collecting this data was a pre- and post-survey using a Likert scale (e.g., from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The surveys helped determine whether teachers felt more confident and capable of applying technology-based strategies in their lessons after completing the PD session.

Implementation Timeline

The entire quantitative data collection process took two weeks and included the following steps:

Week 1 – Pre-Survey Administration:

One week before the professional development session, teachers received an online pre-survey through email or a secure link. This survey gathered baseline information about their current comfort level, frequency of technology use, and confidence in engaging students through interactive tools. The data from this survey helped identify each teacher's starting point before PD training.

Professional Development Delivery:

Teachers then participated in a PD session designed to improve their knowledge and confidence in using interactive technology tools (such as virtual labs, online simulations, or collaboration platforms). The PD provided hands-on practice, examples

of best practices, and opportunities for teachers to reflect on how these strategies could fit into their own lessons.

Week 2 – Post-Survey Administration:

One week after the PD session, teachers received a post-survey via email. They had a full week to complete it. The post-survey included the same Likert-scale items as the pre-survey to measure any change in confidence and comfort using technology to engage students. This one-week window gave participants time to apply what they learned in their classrooms before reflecting on their experiences.

Once both surveys were completed, the results were compared to identify changes in teachers' self-reported confidence levels. The analysis included calculating averages (means) and identifying percentage increases or decreases in specific areas such as comfort using digital tools, frequency of integrating interactive technology, and perceived student engagement. These comparisons provided measurable evidence of whether the PD improved teacher confidence and supported the intended instructional goals.

Potential Challenges and Solutions

A few possible obstacles affected the survey process:

Limited Time:

Teachers often had busy schedules that made it difficult to complete surveys promptly. To address this, the surveys were short, easy to access online, and sent with reminders to encourage timely participation.

Low Participation or Buy-In:

Some teachers did not feel motivated to complete the surveys if they were

unsure how the PD would benefit them. To increase buy-in, the purpose of the study was clearly explained, emphasizing that the results would directly support professional growth and classroom improvement.

Survey Fatigue:

Long or repetitive surveys discouraged full participation. To prevent this, both the pre- and post-surveys were designed to take no more than 10 minutes to complete and use simple, clearly worded questions.

By focusing on pre- and post-surveys, this quantitative approach provided clear, data-driven insights into how professional development impacted teachers' confidence in integrating interactive technology. The information gathered helped school leaders understand the effectiveness of the PD and guided future decisions about teacher support and training initiatives.

Data Analysis

This research project used quantitative data to examine how professional development in interactive technology affected teachers' confidence in high school science classes. Following WGU's exempt research policy, all information came only from teacher participants through pre- and post-surveys.

The data from both surveys were entered into a spreadsheet or simple statistical software. The average score (mean) for each survey question was calculated for both the pre-survey and the post-survey. These mean scores were then compared to see whether teachers' confidence improved after professional development. For example, if the average score for "I feel confident using digital tools in class" increased from 3.2 before the PD to 4.4 after, it showed a positive change in teacher confidence.

The analysis also included calculating percentages and frequency distributions to identify patterns or trends in teacher responses. This helped show how often teachers reported feeling more confident or using technology more frequently after the training.

By comparing averages, percentages, and response frequencies from before and after professional development, this analysis clearly showed whether the training helped teachers feel more confident and prepared to use interactive technology in their classrooms. The results provided simple, descriptive evidence of growth in teacher confidence and improvements in instructional practice.

Data Security and Confidentiality

I kept all research data secure by storing it on my password-protected personal computer, which was accessible only to me. All digital files, including survey responses, observation notes, interview transcripts, and reflective journals, were saved in secure folders and were not stored on shared drives, cloud-based public platforms, or external devices. I maintained confidentiality by removing all identifying information from the data and assigning participants codes or pseudonyms. I did not include names, job titles, or any personally identifiable details in my notes, transcripts, or reports. All data was used solely for this study and was not shared with administrators, colleagues, or any unauthorized individuals, ensuring participant privacy and confidentiality throughout the research process.

Conclusion

This action research examined how professional development centered on interactive technology influenced teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies in high school science classrooms, using quantitative data as the primary source of analysis.

Pre- and post-survey results were analyzed to measure changes in teachers' self-reported confidence and frequency of technology integration. The expected result was an increase in mean survey scores following professional development, indicating improved teacher confidence and more consistent use of interactive technology to support student engagement.

Chapter 4: Results

Results Introduction

This action research project focused on strengthening teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies through professional development centered on interactive technology in grades 9–12 science classrooms at Salt Cedar High School (pseudonym). The research addressed the problem that many science teachers lacked confidence in integrating interactive, technology-based instructional strategies, which limited their ability to implement engaging, student-centered lessons and often resulted in traditional, teacher-directed instruction. The guiding research question was: How does participating in professional development impact teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies?

To address this question, a targeted professional development session was designed and implemented to improve teachers' confidence in integrating interactive technology into their instruction. The PD consisted of a structured, hands-on workshop that introduced teachers to practical digital tools such as virtual labs, interactive simulations, real-time formative assessment platforms, and collaborative online applications. The session included modeling of inquiry-based science lessons that incorporated technology, guided practice where teachers explored and created sample activities aligned to their curriculum, and opportunities for collaborative planning and discussion. Teachers were also provided with troubleshooting strategies, classroom management tips for technology-rich environments, and time to reflect on how these tools could increase student participation and engagement in their specific content areas.

Using a quantitative design aligned with WGU's exempt research guidelines, data was collected solely from teacher participants through pre- and post-surveys utilizing a

Likert scale. These surveys measured changes in teachers' self-reported confidence levels and frequency of technology integration. The findings presented in Part C showed increases in mean survey scores from pre- to post-assessment, along with higher percentages of teachers indicating agreement or strong agreement with confidence-related statements after professional development. These results directly answered the research question by providing measurable evidence that participation in professional development positively impacted teachers' confidence in implementing engagement strategies. Overall, the project demonstrated a clear connection between targeted professional development and improved teacher confidence, supporting data-informed decisions to strengthen instructional practices.

Findings

Figure 1

The graph shows a clear comparison of teachers' confidence levels before and after participating in the professional development session, using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree). The results are based on four teachers (n = 4), and the pattern of growth across all eight survey items is consistent and noticeable.

For the first item, confidence in integrating technology into lessons, teachers started at an average of about 3.0, which reflects moderate confidence. After the professional development, the average increased to approximately 4.2, showing a meaningful gain. This suggests that teachers felt much more comfortable incorporating digital tools into their daily instruction.

When asked about regularly using digital tools, the pre-survey average was around 2.8, one of the lower starting points. Following the training, the average increased to about 4.0. This shift indicates that teachers moved from occasional or uncertain use toward feeling prepared to use digital tools more consistently.

For comfort with troubleshooting technology issues, teachers initially averaged about 2.9, showing some hesitation in handling technical challenges. After the professional development, the average rose to approximately 4.1, suggesting that teachers felt more capable of managing technology-related problems during instruction.

On the statement about whether technology tools help students understand content better, teachers began at about 3.4, indicating moderate agreement. After the PD session, the average increased to roughly 4.4. This growth shows that teachers strengthened their belief in the instructional value of interactive technology.

Regarding the use of digital platforms to support inquiry-based learning, the pre-survey mean was around 3.0. After the training, it increased to approximately 4.2,

reflecting stronger confidence in using technology to promote exploration and critical thinking in science.

For designing collaborative lessons using technology, teachers initially averaged about 2.9. Post-survey results showed an increase to approximately 4.1, indicating that teachers felt more prepared to create student-centered, collaborative activities supported by digital tools.

One of the lowest starting points was the item on using technology for real-time checks for understanding, which averaged around 2.8 before the PD. Afterward, the average increased to about 4.0, suggesting improved confidence in using digital formative assessment strategies during instruction.

Finally, because of the belief that technology increases student motivation, teachers began with an average of approximately 3.5, already leaning toward agreement. After the PD, the average rose to about 4.5, indicating even stronger agreement that interactive technology positively influences student engagement and motivation.

Overall, the pre-survey averages ranged from about 2.8 to 3.5, while the post-survey averages increased to between 4.0 and 4.5. Every item showed growth of approximately one full point or more on the Likert scale. Even with a small group of four participants, the consistent upward trend across all areas provides clear evidence that professional development strengthened teachers' confidence in using interactive technology to support student engagement in high school science classrooms.

Answers to the Research Questions

The research question guiding this study was: How does participating in professional development impact teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies?

Based on the analysis of the pre- and post-survey data, the results clearly show that professional development had a positive impact on teacher confidence. Before the training, teachers reported moderate confidence levels, with average scores generally around the neutral to slightly agree range on the 5-point Likert scale. Areas such as regularly using digital tools, troubleshooting technology issues, and using technology for real-time checks for understanding reflected some hesitation. After the professional development session, all survey items showed noticeable increases in mean scores, with teachers reporting stronger agreement across every category. This growth indicates that teachers felt more confident integrating interactive technology into their science lessons, designing collaborative and inquiry-based activities, and using digital tools to assess student understanding. Even belief-based items, such as whether technology increases student motivation, showed improvement. Although the participant group was small ($n = 4$), the consistent upward trend across all eight survey questions provides clear quantitative evidence that participation in professional development strengthened teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies supported by interactive technology.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusion

Discussion and Conclusion Introduction

This action research study sets out to determine whether professional development focused on interactive technology could strengthen teachers' confidence in using engagement strategies in high school science classrooms. After analyzing the pre- and post-survey data, the overall conclusion is clear: the professional development made a meaningful difference in how confident teachers felt about integrating technology into their instruction. Before the training, teachers expressed moderate confidence levels, suggesting that while they recognized the value of interactive tools, they were not fully comfortable using them consistently or strategically. However, after participating in the professional development session, teachers reported noticeable growth across all measured areas.

The findings showed increases in mean scores for every survey item, indicating stronger agreement with statements related to integrating digital tools, designing collaborative and inquiry-based lessons, troubleshooting technology issues, and using technology to monitor student understanding in real time. These improvements suggest that professional development did more than simply introduce tools; it helped teachers feel prepared, supported, and capable of applying those tools in meaningful ways. The growth across both skill-based items and belief-based items further reinforces that the training influenced not only teachers' abilities but also their perceptions of how technology supports student engagement.

Although the study involved a small group of four participants, the consistent upward trend across all survey responses strengthens the credibility of the conclusions.

The data provides quantitative evidence that structured, hands-on professional development can build teacher confidence and encourage more intentional use of interactive engagement strategies. Overall, the study concludes that when teachers are given focused training, practical examples, and time to reflect, they are more likely to feel empowered to implement technology in ways that promote active learning and student engagement in high school science classrooms.

Problem Solutions

The original problem at Salt Cedar High School was that many science teachers did not feel confident using interactive engagement strategies, especially those involving technology. Because of this, instruction often stayed traditional and teacher-centered, which limited opportunities for students to actively participate and fully engage with science content. The results of this study connect directly to that concern. The data showed that once teachers participated in focused professional development, their confidence increased across all areas measured in the survey.

The findings suggest that the issue was not that teachers were unwilling to use technology, but rather that they needed structured support and practical experience. After receiving hands-on training, examples of how to use digital tools effectively, and time to reflect on how these strategies could fit into their lessons, teachers felt more capable and prepared. They reported greater confidence integrating technology into instruction, supporting inquiry-based learning, designing collaborative activities, troubleshooting technical challenges, and using digital tools to check for student understanding. This

growth indicates that building teacher confidence is a realistic and achievable solution to the original problem.

To address this issue long term, schools can continue offering targeted professional development that goes beyond a single workshop. Ongoing support such as collaborative planning time, peer sharing, lesson modeling, and follow-up coaching can help teachers continue building confidence and refining their practice. Creating a supportive environment where teachers feel comfortable trying new strategies is also important. When teachers know they have access to resources and assistance, they are more likely to move away from traditional lecture methods and toward more interactive, student-centered instruction.

In conclusion, the results of this study show that the research problem can be addressed by intentionally investing in teacher confidence through meaningful professional development. When teachers feel prepared and supported, they are better equipped to create engaging science classrooms that encourage active participation and deeper learning.

Limitations

Although the findings of this study suggest that professional development helped increase teacher confidence, there are several limitations that should be acknowledged. One of the most important limitations was the small number of participants. With only four teachers involved in the study, the results cannot be generalized to a larger group or different school settings. Because the sample size was small, even slight changes in one participant's responses could noticeably affect the overall averages. While the upward

trend in the data was clear, the limited number of participants may have influenced the strength of the conclusions.

Another limitation is that the study relied entirely on self-reported survey responses. Teachers rated their own confidence levels, which means the data reflect their personal perceptions. It is possible that participants may have felt encouraged to show improvement after attending the professional development session. Additionally, the study did not include classroom observations or objective measures to confirm whether increased confidence resulted in consistent instructional changes. Therefore, the findings represent perceived growth rather than direct evidence of long-term classroom impact.

Time was also a factor during implementation. Professional development and data collection occurred within a short period, which may not have allowed teachers enough time to fully apply and refine the strategies they learned. Confidence can continue to grow with practice, and a longer follow-up period might have shown even greater changes. Teachers' busy schedules and daily responsibilities may have also limited how deeply they were able to explore and implement new technology tools.

Another challenge was the variation in teachers' prior experience with technology. Some participants entered the study already feeling somewhat comfortable with digital tools, while others had less experience. These differences may have influenced how much growth was reflected in the survey results. Teachers who started with higher confidence may have shown smaller increases, while those with lower starting confidence may have demonstrated more noticeable gains.

Finally, external factors such as access to reliable technology, internet connectivity, and student familiarity with digital tools may have influenced how teachers

experienced implementation. Even when devices are available, technical issues or student readiness can impact how confidently teachers feel using interactive technology in real classroom settings.

Despite these limitations, the study still provides meaningful insight into how professional development can support teacher confidence. Recognizing these challenges allows the findings to be interpreted realistically and offers direction for improving future research and professional development efforts.

Implications

The findings of this study have important implications for educational leadership practice, particularly in supporting teacher confidence and strengthening instructional quality. The results showed that targeted professional development significantly increased teachers' confidence in using interactive technology and engagement strategies. This suggests that school leaders play a critical role in creating systems of support that build teacher capacity rather than simply introducing new tools or initiatives.

One key implication is that professional development should be intentional, practical, and ongoing. The growth seen in this study indicates that teachers benefit most from hands-on training, clear modeling of strategies, and time to reflect on how new tools fit into their specific content areas. Educational leaders should move beyond one-time workshops and instead design sustained professional learning opportunities that include follow-up support, collaborative planning time, and peer sharing. When leaders prioritize

structured, continuous learning, teachers are more likely to develop both confidence and competence.

Another implication is the importance of fostering a culture of instructional risk-taking and collaboration. The study suggests that when teachers feel supported and prepared, they are more willing to try new engagement strategies. School leaders can strengthen this by encouraging professional learning communities, creating spaces for teachers to share successes and challenges, and recognizing growth in instructional practice. Leadership that promotes trust and collaboration can reduce hesitation and increase innovation in the classroom.

The findings also highlight the need for leaders to align technological initiatives with instructional goals. Simply providing devices or digital platforms is not enough. Leaders must ensure that teachers understand how technology supports student engagement, inquiry, collaboration, and formative assessment. Professional development should clearly connect digital tools to learning outcomes rather than treating technology as an add-on.

Additionally, educational leaders must consider equity when implementing technology-based strategies. Providing consistent access to devices, reliable internet, and technical support is essential for both teachers and students. Leaders should assess infrastructure, troubleshoot barriers, and allocate resources strategically to ensure that confidence gained through training can be sustained in practice.

Finally, this study reinforces the idea that teacher confidence is a foundational element of instructional improvement. When leaders invest in building teacher confidence, they are indirectly supporting student engagement and academic success.

Strengthening teacher capacity should remain a central focus of leadership decisions related to curriculum, professional development, and instructional reform.

Overall, the implications of this study suggest that educational leaders can meaningfully impact classroom engagement by prioritizing sustained professional development, fostering a collaborative culture, and aligning technology integration with clear instructional goals. By doing so, leaders create conditions in which teachers feel empowered to implement innovative engagement strategies that benefit student learning.

Further Investigation

While this study showed that professional development helped increase teachers' confidence in using interactive technology, it also opened the door to additional questions that deserve further exploration. One important next step would be to examine whether the increase in teacher confidence leads to long-term changes in classroom practice and measurable improvements in student engagement and achievement. This study focused on teachers' perceptions of their confidence, but future research could include classroom observations, student input, or academic performance data to better understand how teacher growth affects student outcomes.

It would also be helpful to look at the long-term impact of professional development. A follow-up study conducted several months later could determine whether teachers continue to use interactive technology consistently and whether their confidence remains strong over time. Ongoing support, such as coaching or collaborative

professional learning communities, could also be examined to see if it helps maintain and deepen teacher growth beyond the initial training.

Another area worth exploring is how different types of professional development influence teacher confidence. Comparing one-time workshops to sustained coaching models or collaborative planning sessions could provide insight into which approaches are most effective. Understanding what type of support leads to lasting instructional change would help schools design more meaningful professional learning experiences.

Future research could also explore how teacher background and experience levels influence growth. Teachers with different years of experience or varying levels of prior technology exposure may respond differently to professional development. Examining these differences could help leaders provide more targeted and personalized support. Additionally, factors such as technology access, internet reliability, and student familiarity with digital tools may influence how confidently teachers implement new strategies. Investigating these contextual elements would help schools better understand the practical barriers that can affect technological integration.

Finally, expanding the study to include a larger and more diverse group of teachers across multiple schools would strengthen the findings and allow for broader conclusions. A larger sample size could confirm whether the positive trends seen in this study are consistent in different educational settings.

Overall, this research serves as a starting point for continued exploration of how professional development shapes teacher confidence and classroom engagement. Continued investigation in these areas can help educators and leaders refine their strategies and create stronger, more engaging learning experiences for students.

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Appendix A

Teacher Confidence in Interactive Technology Survey

Purpose: This survey is designed to measure teacher confidence in using interactive technology to engage students in high school science classes. Responses will be collected for pre- and post-professional development.

Instructions:

Please rate each statement using the scale below:

1 = Strongly Disagree

2 = Disagree

3 = Neutral

4 = Agree

5 = Strongly Agree

Survey Items

- _____ 1. I feel confident integrating interactive technology into my science lessons.
- _____ 2. I regularly use digital tools to increase student engagement.
- _____ 3. I feel comfortable troubleshooting basic technology issues during instruction.
- _____ 4. I believe interactive digital tools help students better understand science concepts.
- _____ 5. I know how to use digital platforms to support inquiry-based learning.
- _____ 6. I feel confident designing lessons that use technology for collaboration among students.
- _____ 7. I can effectively use technology to check student understanding in real-time.
- _____ 8. I believe interactive technology increases student motivation in science.

Appendix B

November 14, 2025

Dear *Rodolfo Balagtas, II*,

Dishchii'bikoh High School has reviewed your Capstone Research request for study, titled *Empowering High School Science Learning Through Technology Integration*, and we agree to support collaboration efforts towards your collection of data in accordance with your description:

This action research focuses on improving student engagement in high school science classes through the integration of interactive technology and professional development that builds teacher confidence in using these tools. The study involves 2 to 4 science teachers from a rural high school in the southwestern United States who teach grades 9–12 and represent diverse backgrounds and experience levels. Participants will apply technology-based strategies in their classrooms and reflect on how these practices enhance engagement and instructional effectiveness.

The extended invitation to conduct the above-described study will occur between November 21, 2025, to January 20, 2026.

Sincerely,

Mr. Phil Endfield

Dishchii'bikoh High School Principal

Dishchii'bikoh Community School

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phil.endfield@dishchiibikoh.org

Appendix C

Primary Artifact: PD PowerPoint Presentation and Professional Development Training

Manual

Empowering High School Science Learning Through Interactive Technology

- Salt Lake High School
- Grades 9-12 Science Professional Development

1

Purpose of Today's Training

- Strengthen teacher confidence in integrating technology
 - Increase understanding of effective science classroom
 - Provide practical, real-time strategies

2

Workshop Objectives

- Identify engagement challenges
 - Integrate science & interactive tech tools
 - Design inquiry-based digital lessons
 - Evaluate and improve assessment
 - Troubleshoot common tech challenges

3

Why Student Engagement Matters

- Engage more often, achieve more
 - Increase learning, retention, performance
 - Technology supports inquiry and collaboration
 - Models real-world science digital learning

4

Interactive Technology Tools

- Virtual Labs & Simulations
 - Real-Time Performance Assessment Platforms
 - Collaborative Digital Tools
 - Immersive Professional Platforms

5

Modified Lesson Framework (5E Model)

- Engage - Digital phenomena
 - Explore - Virtual lab investigations
 - Explain - Digital collaboration
 - Elaborate - Real-world phenomena
 - Evaluate - Real-world assessment

6

Hands-On Planning Activity

- Select a science standard
 - Integrate science and digital tool
 - Create a rubric/assessment
 - Design a digital interactive assessment

7

Troubleshooting & Classroom Management

- Off-task behavior → Directed tasks & time limits
- Tech issues → Backup plan ready
- Unengaged participants → Assign digital roles
- Limited resources → Downloadable activities

8

Implementation Timeline

- Week 1 - The Survey
 - Week 2 - PD Workshop
 - Week 3 - Classroom Implementation
 - Week 4 - Post-Survey
 - Ongoing - Peer collaboration and coaching

9

Measuring Impact

- Confidence integrating technology
 - Content understanding
 - Designing collaborative lessons
 - Evaluating and improving assessment

10

Sustainability Plan

- Identify technology-staffing solutions
 - Shared digital resource hub
 - Peer collaboration and tech refreshment
 - Administrative support and maintenance

11

Reflection & Commitment

- What tool will you implement next week?
 - What opportunities remained?
 - How will this impact your student engagement?

12

The primary artifact of this project is the Professional Development Training Manual that was created and used as the final product of the proposed solution. The manual outlines the purpose, agenda, technology tools, modeled lessons, hands-on activities, implementation timeline, and evaluation process used to strengthen teachers' confidence in integrating interactive technology into high school science instruction. This training manual represents the completed intervention delivered during the study. It will be attached separately with this submission in accordance with the artifact guidelines.